

Synthesis of Novel Organic Monomers Capable of Exhibiting Non-linear Optical Properties

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The synthesis and optical characteristics of a series of *trans*-(*p*-aminostyryl)-pyridines and their derivatives are reported. These molecules were obtained as precursors for the synthesis of polymers with the aim of incorporating into the structure non linear optical activity.

In recent years the ability to obtain high values of the non-linear optical coefficients in single crystals and some organic polymer films has become well established^{1,2}. Values of the non-linear optical coefficients equal to and greater than those found in inorganic crystals such as lithium niobate have been observed in either organic single crystals or poled polymer films³. The initial research in this area has to a large extent been concentrated on the area of organic single crystals, however recently high values of the non-linear optical coefficients have been observed with poled polymer films. These latter systems are usually molecular dispersions of the active organic molecules in optically transparent polymer films. Ideally, the active element might be an intrinsic part of the polymer structure; this would increase the activity per unit volume and hence the overall efficiency of the films. In this communication, the synthesis and absorption characteristics of a series of related molecules with potential non-linear optical properties and which are also suitable as precursors for polymer synthesis, are described.

For an organic molecule to exhibit a high non-linear optical coefficient it is generally accepted that the structure should contain both donor and acceptor groups which are part of the same conjugated system. It is also important that the molecules should be capable of forming a non-centrosymmetric crystal structure. An example of such a structure would be 2-methyl-4-nitroaniline, which can be crystallised into a non-centrosymmetric crystalline form and it exhibits non-linear optical properties. If the crystal formed is centrosymmetric, dipole alignment in adjacent molecules will lead to cancellation of the non-linear effects. Studies of second harmonic generation (SHG) in 2-methyl-4-nitroaniline have indicated that it can exhibit values which are almost

two thousand times those for LiNbO_3 , the most commonly used inorganic material. Ideally, the use of aligned polymer films would have the advantage of allowing the use of conventional thin film processing technology to generate the components required for active optical circuits.

Selection of molecules for investigation: Of the organic molecules capable of exhibiting high non-linear optical coefficients, styryl molecules have been found to exhibit as molecules in solution some of the highest values. The monomers synthesised here have not only to contain the optically active group, but also be capable of reaction to give polymeric structures. The general structure chosen for this programme of study was as follows:

where $X = \text{CH}_3, \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$ or H and $Y = \text{OH}, \text{COOH}$ etc. Quaternisation of the pyridine ring (Z) gives the potential of producing shifts in the optical absorption spectrum and also the introduction of a further functional group necessary for polymerization via a step growth procedure. If the optical axis is considered to lie from the amine to the pyridine group, then two types of polymer can arise, one with the vector in the chain direction and the other with it

perpendicular to the chain structure. Studies of liquid crystalline polymers have shown that poling can induce alignment of the chains and it is therefore important to be able to generate both type of structures. A number of styryl and (*p*-aminostyryl)-pyridinium dyes and their derivatives are known⁴ and some of these dyes are useful in the photographic industry as sensitisers⁵ and also as electrochromic probes for membrane potential. In this communication, we consider the synthesis of monomer precursors for the generation of non-linear active polymers via either grafting to vinyl polymers containing vinyl backbone or through condensation reactions for difunctional derivatives.

Results and Discussion

Synthesis of these styryl type of compounds can be carried out using either aldol condensation or via a palladium-catalysed coupling (Heck reaction); both the routes were explored and the latter was found to be the more efficient. The synthesis carried out following the method of Hassner *et al.*⁴. Good yields were obtained from the palladium-catalysed coupling of olefins with an appropriate aromatic halide. In all the cases, the catalyst used was palladium acetate (1 mol %) together with tri-*o*-tolyl phosphine (2 mol %) in dry triethylamine; the reaction required heating, at 100–110° for 48–72 h under an atmosphere of nitrogen and yields varied between 40 and 80% depending upon the nature of the substituents on the aniline ring.

4-Bromoaniline (2) and *p*-(*N,N*-disubstituted)-bromoanilines formed 60–80% yield of styryl products with 4-vinylpyridine (3).

4a; R₁=R₂=H
 4b; R₁=R₂=CH₃
 4c; R₁=R₂=C₂H₅

7a; R₁=H, R₂=CH₃
 7b; R₁=H, R₂=C₂H₅
 7c; R₁=H, R₂=COCH₃

The compounds 4a and 4c could be converted into positively charged pyridinium dyes 5 and 6 on treatment with methyl iodide and ethyl bromoacetate respectively. Quaternisation reaction proceeded with preferential reaction at the less hindered pyridine nitrogen and leads to distinct colour changes in the monomers consistent with the changes in the electron density distribution.

4-Bromo-*N*-methyl, ethyl, acetyl anilines all undergo palladium-catalysed addition to the olefins 7a–c in 50–70% overall yield. Similarly, methyl *p*-bromo-β-anilinopropionate (8a) reacts with slight excess of vinyl pyridine and a palladium acetate catalyst to form *trans*-styrylpyridine derivative (8b) in reasonable yield. This propionic ester was then hydrolysed to the acid (8c). The ester and the acid are both thermally stable melting at 143 and 244° respectively. We are currently exploring the conversion of the acid (8c) to the acid chloride and thence via reaction with a polymer with pendant hydroxy functions to the polymer, hopefully by a single stage process.

Generation of *trans*-[*p*-(*n*-adipoylamino)styryl]pyridine (9): The aim of this synthesis was to explore the possible condensation reaction of amine and in the initial synthesis to prepare the dimer. The reaction was carried out between adipoyl chloride and the monomer 4a. The product isolated was the acid 9 rather than the dimer. The acid is also a possible route to a polymer in that it is capable of quaternisation of the pyridine to give a unit in which the monomer is aligned along the backbone.

The monomers isolated uptill now are symmetric and hence have the possibility of crystallising in a non-optically active centrosymmetric form. In order to destroy the symmetry we have investigated the synthesis of a non-centrosymmetric monomer 10.

For example, 2-methyl-4-bromoaniline when coupled with 4-vinylpyridine produced *trans*-[*p*-(2-methyl-amino)styryl]pyridine in 50% yield.

In all these reactions with palladium-catalysed reactions of organic halides with olefins we have isolated only the *E(trans)*-isomers as observed by nmr coupling. The olefinic protons in **4c** shows a simple AB-pattern centred at 7 ppm with a coupling constant of 15.7 Hz typical of a *trans*-configuration. These reactions are important because they accomplish a transformation not achievable in one operational step by any other method. Similar phenomena have been observed for 4-[*p*-(*s*-di-*n*-butylamino)styryl]pyridinium dyes⁴.

In all the cases cited, elemental analysis, nmr and mass spectral data were consistent with the structures shown. The mass spectra showed significant molecular ion peaks. Many of the *para*-aminostyrylpyridine compounds are stable at room temperature. The nmr spectra were compared with TMS as internal standard. Unless otherwise stated, all the R_f values were obtained using ethyl acetate as solvent.

It is clear from this study that it is possible to produce a wide variety of derivatives whilst retaining the same spectral absorption characteristics. The process of quaternisation of the pyridine group has, as expected, the largest effect in terms of shifts in the optical spectra. Shifts of the order of 100 nm are observed on quaternisation. Some of the above derivatives have the potential of being attached to functionalised vinyl polymers, in particular, poly(methacryloyl chloride). This has been carried out and will be discussed elsewhere. Alternatively, the molecules such as **9** have the ability to form polymers by condensation. Attempts to achieve a high molecular weight polymer proved to be unsuccessful, possibly as a result of non-stoichiometry in the starting material.

Experimental

Synthesis of *trans*-4-[*p*-(*di*-*N*-ethylamino)styryl]pyridine (4c**):** A mixture of *p*-bromo-*N,N*-diethylaniline (4.56 g, 0.02 mol), 4-vinylpyridine (2.63 g, 0.025 mol), palladium diacetate (45 mg, 0.0002 mol), tri-*o*-tolylphosphine (120 mg, 0.004 mol) and dry triethylamine (10 ml) was heated at 100–110° for

72 h in a carius tube that was flushed with nitrogen. The tube was cooled and the solid yellow reaction mixture was separated between water and a large volume of methylene chloride. The combined methylene chloride solutions was washed with water, dried over magnesium sulphate and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The resulting solid (**4c**) was recrystallised twice from chloroform-methanol mixture as pale yellow crystals (4.2 g), m.p. 178–80°; in some cases purification of the products were carried out by chromatography on silica gel by using benzene-chloroform (2 : 1) as eluent (Found : C, 80.87; H, 7.88; N, 11.08. $C_{17}H_{20}N_2$ requires : C, 80.95; H, 7.93; N, 11.11%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 390 nm; δ (CDCl₃) 8.52 (2H, d, J 6.5 Hz, α), 7.40 (2H, d, J 6.5 Hz, β), 7.20 (1H, d, J 15.7 Hz, V_2), 6.72 (1H, d, J 15.7 Hz, V_1), 7.28 (2H, d, J 8.5 Hz, *ortho*), 6.65 (2H, d, J 8.6 Hz, *meta*), 3.39 (4H, m, N-CH₂CH₃) and 1.2 (6H, t, N-CH₂CH₃); m/z (rel. int.) 252 (80, M^+) and 237 (100, $M-15$ base peak).

Quaternisation : 1-(Carbethoxymethyl)-4-[*p*-*di*-*n*-ethylamino]styryl]pyridinium bromide (6**):** The styrylpyridine (**4c**; 0.5 g) was suspended in toluene (10 ml) and stirred at 90° whilst ethyl bromoacetate (0.4 g, 1.2 eq) was added dropwise. Almost immediately a red colour was formed. After a further 1 h, bromoacetate (0.1 g) was added to it and the mixture was refluxed for 3 h. The solvent was then removed, the products were chromatographed (silica; dichloromethane→dichloromethane/ethanol 10 : 1) and the resulting red solid was recrystallised from ethanol-hexane mixture, (0.3 g), m.p. 188–90° (Found : C, 60.05; H, 6.40; N, 6.53. $C_{21}H_{27}BrN_2O_2$ requires : C, 60.14; H, 6.44; N, 6.68%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 492 nm; ν_{max} 1720 cm⁻¹ (C=O); m/z 338/339 (70/65), 252 (88, 339–87) and 237 (85).

***Trans*-4-[*p*-(*amino*)styryl]pyridine (**4a**):** Following the general procedure, *p*-bromoaniline (3.44 g, 0.02 mol) and 4-vinylpyridine (**3**) were converted into a light yellow solid (**4a**; 2.2 g, 50%), m.p. 245°d (Found : C, 79.48; H, 6.10; N, 14.20. $C_{13}H_{12}N_2$ requires : C, 79.59; H, 6.12; N, 14.29%); R_f 0.7; λ_{max} (EtOH) 368 nm; ν_{max} 3400 cm⁻¹ (NH); δ (CDCl₃) 5.40 (2H, b, NH₂), 6.55 (1H, d, V_1), (1H, d, V_2); m/z 196 (100, M^+ , base peak) and 168 (42, $M-28$).

1-Methyl-4-[*p*-(*amino*)styryl]pyridinium iodide (5**):** A mixture of *trans*-styrylpyridine (**4a**) and methyl iodide (1.2 equiv.) in methanol was kept for 2 days. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the resulting red solid was crystallised from acetone-benzene mixture, (50%), m.p. 250°d; λ_{max} (EtOH) 490 nm; m/z 211 (base peak).

***Trans*-4-[*p*-*di*-*n*-methylamino]styryl]pyridine (**4b**):** Following the general procedure, *p*-bromo-*N,N*-dimethylaniline (4.0 g, 0.02 mol) and 4-vinylpyridine (2.63 g, 0.025 mol) were converted to yellow flacks to **4b** (2.8 g, 60%), m.p. 240° (Found : C, 80.28; H, 7.05; N, 12.45. $C_{15}H_{16}N_2$ requires : C, 80.36; H, 7.14; N, 12.50%); R_f = 0.71; λ_{max} (EtOH) 385 nm; δ (CDCl₃) 8.55 (2H, d, α), 7.32 (2H, d, β), 6.85 (1H,

d, J 15.8 Hz, V_1), 7.30 (1H, d, J 15.8 Hz, V_2), 7.50 (2H, d, *ortho*), 6.70 (2H, d, *meta*) and 3.09 (6H, s, $(CH_3)_2$); m/z 224 (100, M^+ , base peak) and 209 (65, $M-15$).

Trans-4-[*p*-(*n*-methylamino)styryl]pyridine (7a): It was prepared from *p*-bromo-*n*-methylaniline (3.72 g, 0.02 mol) and 4-vinyl pyridine (2.63 g, 0.025 mol) at 110° for 72 h as yellow powder (55%) and crystallised from methanol-chloroform, m.p. 240–42° (Found: C, 80.00; H, 6.53; N, 13.26. $C_{14}H_{14}N_2$ requires: C, 80.00; H, 6.66; N, 13.33%; $R_f=0.83$; λ_{max} (EtOH) 375 nm; δ (CDCl₃) 2.75 (3H, s, N-CH₃) and 3.05 (1H, b, NH); m/z 210 (100, M^+ , base peak) and 180 (60, $M-30$).

Trans-4-[*p*-*n*-ethylamino)styryl]pyridine (7b): It was prepared in the usual way gave 7b (65%, 3 g) as yellow crystals starting from *p*-bromo-*n*-ethylaniline (4.0 g, 0.02 mol) and 4-vinylpyridine (2.63 g, 0.025 mol) at 150° for 70 h, (65%, 3 g), m.p. 200–02° (Found: C, 80.26; H, 7.07; N, 12.42. $C_{15}H_{16}N_2$ requires: C, 80.35; H, 7.14; N, 12.50%; $R_f=0.8$; λ_{max} (EtOH) 380 nm; ν_{max} 3 410 cm⁻¹ (NH); δ (CDCl₃+DMSO) 6.85 (1H, d, V_1), 7.45 (1H, d, V_2), 8.45 (2H, d, α), 7.50 (2H, d, β), 3.20 (2H, b, CH_2CH_3), 1.25 (3H, m, CH_2CH_3) and 2.90 (1H, b, NH); m/z 224 (M^+).

Trans-4-[*p*-*acetyl*amino)styryl]pyridine (7c): Following the general procedure, *p*-bromo-*n*-acetylaniline (4.28 g, 0.02 mol) and 4-vinylpyridine (2.63 g, 0.025 mol) were converted to 7c (3.5 g, 75%) which was crystallised from methanol as a yellow solid, m.p. 168° (Found: C, 75.50; H, 5.80; N, 11.76. $C_{16}H_{14}N_2O$ requires: C, 75.63; H, 5.88; N, 11.76%; λ_{max} (EtOH) 335 nm; ν_{max} 3 410 cm⁻¹ (NH); δ (CDCl₃) 2.25 (3H, s, N-CO-CH₃) and 3.95 (1H, b, NH); m/z 238 (M^+).

Methyl *p*-bromo- β -anilinopropionate (8a): To a mixture of 4-bromoaniline (17.2 g, 0.01 mol) and glacial acetic acid (2.5 ml) was added freshly distilled methyl acrylate (8.6 g, 0.1 mol) during a period of 1 h while the mixture was stirred and heated on a steam-bath, and heating and stirring were further continued for 8 h. The red mixture dissolved in ether was then washed with water (2 × 25 ml) followed by 5% sodium bicarbonate solution and water. After drying, the solvent was removed by distillation under reduced pressure. The resulting solid was crystallised from methanol, (15.5 g), m.p. 65° (Found: C, 47.17; H, 4.70; N, 5.49. $C_{10}H_{12}BrNO_2$ requires: C, 47.42; H, 4.72; N, 5.51%; ν_{max} 3 400 cm⁻¹ (NH); δ (CDCl₃) 7.25 (2H, d), 6.45 (2H, d), 3.7 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.4 (2H, m, NCH₂), 2.59 (2H, m, CH₂COO) and 4.05 (NH).

Trans-4-[methyl- β -anilinopropionate)styryl]pyridine (8b): Following the general procedure, methyl-*p*-bromo- β -anilinopropionate (8a; 5.16 g, 0.02 mol) and 4-vinylpyridine (2.63 g, 0.025 mol) were

heated for 72 h, and 8b (40%) was obtained as yellow crystals, m.p. 143° (Found: C, 72.30; H, 6.32; N, 9.82. $C_{17}H_{18}N_2O_2$ requires: C, 72.34; H, 6.38; N, 9.93%; $R_f=0.7$; λ_{max} (EtOH) 370 nm; ν_{max} (nujol) 3 390 (NH) and 1 710 cm⁻¹ (C=O); δ (CDCl₃) 6.75 (1H, d, V_1), 7.19 (1H, d, V_2), 6.55 (2H, d, m), 7.38 (2H, d, O), 4.25 (1H, b, NH), 3.69 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 3.45 (2H, t, NCH₂) and 2.60 (2H, t, CH₂COO); m/z 282 (88.5, M^+), 223 (40, $M-59$), 209 (100, $M-73$, base peak).

Saponification of the ester to the acid (8c): The ester (8b; 1 g) was hydrolysed using methanolic solution of KOH. The usual work-up gave the crude acid 8c (0.5 g) which was crystallised from methanol-ether, m.p. 244°d (Found: C, 71.51; H, 5.95; N, 10.40. $C_{16}H_{16}N_2O_2$ requires: C, 71.64; H, 5.97; N, 10.44%; $R_f=0.14$; λ_{max} (EtOH) 372 nm.

Trans-4-[*p*-(*n*-adipoylamino)styryl]pyridine (9): To a suspension of 4a (1.5 g) in dry benzene (25 ml), was added triethylamine (1.2 ml) while cooling under nitrogen atmosphere. Adipoyl chloride (0.6 ml) in benzene was then added to it dropwise, while the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 15 min and then refluxed for 3 h. The solvent was removed by distillation under reduced pressure and the resulting red solid (1.25 g) was purified by silica gel chromatography using methylene chloride to yield 9, m.p. 230°d (Found: C, 70.32; H, 6.15; N, 8.55. $C_{19}H_{20}N_2O_3$ requires: C, 70.37; H, 6.17; N, 8.64%; λ_{max} (EtOH) 350 nm; m/z 324 (40, M^+), 195 (100, $M-129$, base peak) and 223 (52, $M-101$).

Trans-4-[2-methyl-4-amino)styryl]pyridine (10): Following the general procedure, 2-methyl-4-bromoaniline (3.72 g, 0.02 mol) and 4-vinylpyridine (2.63 g, 0.025 mol) were converted to 10 (1.5 g, 40%), m.p. 228–30° (Found: C, 79.94; H, 5.61; N, 13.22. $C_{14}H_{14}N_2$ requires: C, 80.00; H, 6.67; N, 13.33%; $R_f=0.73$; λ_{max} (EtOH) 255 nm; m/z 210 (100, M^+ , base peak), 195 (50, $M-15$); δ (CDCl₃) 3.65 (2H, b, NH₂), 2.08 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.95 (1H, d, V_2), 6.52 (1H, d, V_1), 8.55 (2H, d, α), 7.2 (2H, d, β).

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